

Gear Pair Fault Detection Using Vibration Analysis Techniques- A Review

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Abstract

In various Industrial and automobile applications, the rotating component like gear plays an important role in the transmission of power. The most common defects are pitting, scoring and in some cases, tooth breakage may also occur in the early stage of failure. The breakdown of such crucial elements may cause heavy losses in the industry. Prediction of defects in gear pairs by analyzing the change in vibration waveform or vibration signal is a very suitable method. The extraction of defective data is covered under the noise of other gear pairs. In this paper the review of gear of fault detection by using vibration analysis technique for the assessment of the condition of gear pairs for a helical gearbox. The defects are created and behavior of vibration is observed. Some of the advanced techniques of vibration analysis are presented. The effectiveness of vibration techniques is discussed and further research in the detection of any type of damage in gear is analyzed.

Keywords: *Fault detection; Gear pair; Vibration signal analysis.*

Introduction:

Many of the rotating elements like gears, bearing, etc has increased in its area of application day by day and also in the field of manufacturing, automobiles, oil and gas refinery, and nuclear power station, etc. Nowadays these rotating elements have increased greatly with the industrial revolution. The faults may be induced in any of the machinery are due to bearing and gear defects. These faults play a very important role in machinery failure. This machinery fault may lead to catastrophic failure. Under these circumstances, the monitoring of the gear can be done by the vibration analysis technique. This technique is commonly used for the exact evaluation of the health condition of rotating elements or machinery [1]. The effectiveness and reliability of the machinery under rotation are of crucial perception in various industries. The machine maintenance and monitoring the condition is very helpful to maintain the effectiveness of the machine's desirable level. For diagnosing a critical part of the rotating machine an effective vibration signal extraction technique is required [2]. The condition of the different gearboxes was estimated using various vibration analysis techniques including a few statistical measures, enveloping and spectral kurtosis [3]. Experimentation of the vibration signals for some cases like no teeth damage and multiple tooth damage with controllable wear gear sets in the test rig. A comparison between experimental and numerically simulated results are examined with time and frequency domain[4]. In some of the applications of locomotives like railways, these defects can be observed in gear transmission systems. If the defect happens in the gear, its effectiveness and performance will be reduced, and it may cause severe consequences of failure such as the crash of the train and derailment. To prevent these serious problems, it is essential to increase the performance of the gear transmission systems for the safety and reliability of the system [5]. Nowadays the demand for condition monitoring and vibration analysis is used to minimize the consequences of machine failure, but also to utilize the available resources more effectively [6].

2.Review:

Ragini Sidar *et al* (2015) reviewed about vibration-based fault diagnosis in rolling element bearing and vibration analysis techniques. The key points for doing work are the measurement of vibration in time and frequency domain. The feature extraction and diagnosis of the fault, we may use the time and frequency domain. This technique shows the faults in the bearing but it cannot identify the location. The location of the faults in the bearings is indicated by the frequency domain technique[7].

Deepika S *et al* (2016) has proposed analysis of fault in the gear rotor mechanism for measurement of different parameters in gear signal by using dual-tree Complex. The effectiveness of the proposed method is analyzed by using acoustic signal analysis. The health condition of gear, gear damage detection and measurement of the angle between multiple teeth damage is also analyzed. The multiple fault condition is identified from the gear mesh by the generation of the signal. It has a disadvantage that it is unable to identify all types and categories of gear fault [8].

Ajanalkar *et al* (2016) discussed below according to the fault condition i) whenever the damaged tooth meshes impact happens to another gear tooth. So the peak is observed for every 0.2 seconds. ii) In each revolution of meeting gear, the damaged tooth carries in mesh for double teeth damage pinion [9]. Shalaan A.M *et al* (2019) in his experimental test which is carried out on several sets of gears to examine tooth breakage effect and tooth wear defects on vibration generation of the gearbox. The crest factor, RMS and kurtosis from the time domain technique for normal and affected gearboxes are obtained. It is found that the RMS, crest factor and kurtosis ratios for acceleration response are suitable during fault defects while the time domain is not suitable during monitoring the faults [10].

Nilson Barbieri *et al* (2017) in his work, analyzed and monitored the vibration signals of the advanced gearboxes that are used in buses and trucks. The known damage is monitored through Signal Processing techniques. The analysis of vibration signals in time and frequency domain can be done. To detect the presence of damage these techniques are used to identify its characteristics [11]. The fault size for various test cases of gear fault in the test rig of the wind turbine is predicted by analyzing the vibration signals[12].

Vladimir Dykys (2017) in his paper discussed the modal properties of the analyzed object and problem identification of vibration source. In the field of machine monitoring, few selected Signal Processing techniques were presented. These procedures are useful in solving scientific and Research challenges in reducing the vibration. It is also useful in detecting sources described by tuning the external machine structure and transfer path [13].

Laxmikant S.Dhamande *et al* (2018) developed a method for bearing damage identification and compound gear which are based on continuous wavelet transform and discrete wavelet transform of the vibration signal. The author worked on features in the time-frequency domain for gear fault identification in bearing are evaluated and extracted for compound fault. New features are extracted from the wavelet coefficients plot of the continuous wavelet transform at scales corresponding to gear mesh frequency and its harmonics [14].

Sourabh S.Shahapurkar *et al* (2015) analyzed the damage detection in the gearbox system using the vibration analysis method and he analyzed other different graphs for various faults. If we match the vibration response of a faulty gearbox to the response of a gearbox with known fault. These aspects are very useful for future work [15].

Enayet B. Halim *et al* (2008) proposed a new technique that combines wavelet and time-domain averaging for the detection of faults in gearbox it is in a new method for detection of the gearbox. It is the new method for the detection of gearbox faults. The technique's strength lies in the way it preserves the frequency domain information while performing the average and capturing the deterministic part of the signal for one period removing the variable part efficiently [16].

Sujesh Kumar *et al* (2018) concluded in his review on vibration based fault diagnosis techniques for the components of rotating machinery. For the detection of faults, the wavelet transform gives correct results. The time-domain technique does not give any evidence of fault under different load conditions. By the FFT method, it is not easy to detect the categories of damage. The maintenance cost and can be reduced by the use of a convolution neural network[17].

Fuhao Li *et al* (2019) Proposed a variation mode decomposition and its application to gear fault diagnosis for different working conditions. This method is only for the variation of time and non-stationary signals. The proposed method is based on the various advantages and disadvantages of a data-driven time-frequency analysis. [18].

Xihui Liang *et al* (2015) Proposed and simulated the signals of vibration in various conditions for the planetary gearbox. For the simulation of vibration signal of each gear, and a lumped parameter model is developed including the different types of gear like Sun gear planet gear and ring gear. a proposed mathematical model to consider the transmission path effect and the location of the sensor, the resultant vibration signals are obtained. In the time domain, the symptoms of fault shown in the vibration signals of gear like sun gear. In the frequency domain whenever there is a crack, a large number of sidebands appear [19].

Kobra Heidarbeigi *et al* (2010) worked on local tooth damage in the gearbox, for machine condition signal information was acquired. Analysis of data is required comparing the different plots obtained for every test condition to these expected for the specific fault simulated. Spikes of frequency is determined from the time and frequency graphs and compared theoretically [20].

Rusmir Bajric *et al* (2011) reviewed based on results obtained experimentally compared to the effectiveness of vibration analysis technique for the identification of damage in the gears. The approaches based on the time, frequency modulation of amplitude and also time-synchronous averaging analysis are discussed. The severity of the damage is evaluated by synchronous averaging analysis. In damage identification, the time waveform analysis plays an important role. Upon changing the load the change in amplitude and mesh frequency occurs [21].

Leila Nacib *et al* (2013) studied the effectiveness of some vibration analysis techniques for the identification of the problem, tooth crack in gear and the data is recorded. For the identification of damage, the waveform analysis is very effective. The amplitude of variation at the frequency of rotation occurs during the variation of load. To detect the significant changes the cepstrum technique is very effective. the major advantage of the use of the cepstrum technique is the early identification of damage because it is clear and easier to see changes[22].

Aditendra Jaiswal *et al* (2013) in his study on fault diagnosis of fault in gear by analyzing the vibration signature. as compared to defective and the reference gear the vibration spectrum varies. The deviation in the spectrum of different defective gears like wear, pitting, corrosion is obtained [23].

S. Devendiran *et al* (2016) reviewed vibration-based fault diagnosis and condition monitoring for gear and bearing components. Nowadays the advances in condition monitoring technologies have significantly improved diagnosis and prognosis. However, the correct fault detection and prognosis in rotating parts of machinery remain challenging due to complexities in their mechanical systems and operating conditions [24].

Shawki Abouel-seoud *et al* (2012) in his experimental study on stationary vibration waveform, periodic impulses caused by wind turbine gearbox faults appear in both time domain and frequency domain signals. This carries diagnostic information is of great importance for extracting features of the fault [25].

Al Arbi,Salem (2012) in his thesis on condition monitoring of gear systems using vibration analysis, taken a two-stage helical gearbox and examined under the various operating condition and he has developed a mathematical model in his research Activity. The imperfections in the gearbox are simulated by taking a two-stage helical gearbox. To represent the forces acting between two pairs of gears, a model is developed with a suitable stiffness function of two stages helical gear system. The validation is done against a set of results obtained from the experimental measurements with numerical solution [26].

3.Conclusion:

It has been observed that among all monitoring techniques, vibration analysis is better. For proper diagnosis and also to reduce the cost. The identification of damage for damage detection the time waveform analysis is very useful and various remote fault detection such as pitting, scoring and tooth breakage under different conditions of operation, vibration analysis technique play an important role. Time-domain analysis indicators like root-mean-square, kurtosis and crest factor were applied for detection damage and its irregularities.

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